

Random Number Generators and Seeding for Differential Privacy

NAOISE HOLOHAN, IBM Research Europe – Ireland, Ireland

Differential Privacy (DP) relies on random numbers to preserve privacy, typically utilising Pseudorandom Number Generators (PRNGs) as a source of randomness. In order to allow for consistent reproducibility, testing and bug-fixing in DP algorithms and results, it is important to allow for the seeding of the PRNGs used therein.

In this work, we examine the landscape of Random Number Generators (RNGs), and the considerations software engineers should make when choosing and seeding a PRNG for DP. We hope it serves as a suitable guide for DP practitioners, and includes many lessons learned when implementing seeding for `diffprivlib`.

1 INTRODUCTION

The generation of random numbers on computers typically boils down to two distinct steps performed in series [L'E12], (i) *bit generation*, generating a stream of random bits that can be coerced into uniform variates in $[0, 1)$ or uniformly distributed integers [Knu97, L'E94, L'E98, Nie92, Tez95], and (ii) *bit transformation*, the transformation of these uniform variates to generate random variates from arbitrary distributions [Dev86, Gen03, HLD04].

In this paper, we are concerned with the first of these steps, bit generation, and the considerations engineers and scientists must make when designing and implementing Differential Privacy (DP) systems. Issues around the latter, bit transformation, are beyond the scope of this paper, but are independently of great interest to the DP community, because of the privacy vulnerabilities that have recently been highlighted [HB21, HDH⁺22, JMRO22]. DP, a popular paradigm for privacy-enhancing computations, uses random noise to preserve privacy, and therefore requires care and attention when generating random numbers.

Among the requirements for a good Random Number Generator (RNG) is that it is portable and reproducible to allow for reliable and consistent testing, debugging and reproduction of any results [Hel98, MWKA07].¹ These qualities are also of importance to the DP community. Although sensitive DP releases for publication “in the wild” necessitate the most secure type of randomness – that produced by a Cryptographically Secure Pseudorandom Number Generator (CSPRNG) [KMR⁺20] – non-sensitive DP simulations (*i.e.*, for publication, testing and debugging) typically require a user to be able to reproduce results, and therefore require a seeded RNG.

In this paper, we examine the elements of choosing, implementing and securing an RNG for differential privacy. This includes an introduction to RNGs (Section 2) and typical pitfalls encountered when seeding (Section 4). We largely focus on implementations using the Python programming language, and the Numpy and Scikit-Learn packages (Section 3), with more detailed notes on choices we made for `diffprivlib` [HBMAL19] (Section 5). Nevertheless, we hope the principles are sufficiently covered to allow the reader adapt them to their chosen language(s) and package(s). Additional details are provided by way of footnotes, for those interested in delving deeper.

2 AN OVERVIEW OF THE RANDOM NUMBER GENERATOR

Humans have been seeking sources of randomness for millennia. Long before the advent of modern statistics and probability, randomness has been used in determining fate, playing games and selecting public officials. The humble dice can trace its origins back c. 5000 years [ABE08], while the notion of tossing coins has been considered since as far back as c. 3000 years ago in the *I Ching*.

¹For the purpose of this paper, we refer to a Random Number Generator (RNG) as the component performing the bit generation step only, and not bit transformation.

In more recent times, human computers relied on tables of random numbers for their tasks, a well-known example being the book of one million random digits from the appropriately-named RAND Corporation [RAN55].² Nowadays, randomness has a wide variety of uses across science, art, gaming and other fields, necessitating the requirement to generate vast quantities of random numbers. The US Census Bureau estimated needing 90TB of random bytes to implement differential privacy on its 2020 Census release [GL20].

2.1 Hardware

Hardware RNGs are commonly used for critical tasks (such as cryptography), where the supposed randomness of nature is exploited to generate random numbers. Examples include quantum states [MYC⁺16], cameras and microphones on mobile devices [KŠM07, NCP03] and walls of lava lamps [NMS98]³. On Unix-like operating systems, physical sources including “inter-keyboard timings” are used to fill pools of entropy for generating randomness in `/dev/random` (and `/dev/urandom`, which is preferred by many)⁴.⁵ A discussion on whether these, and other sources, are truly random and unpredictable (*cf.* superdeterminism) is certainly beyond the scope of this paper!

2.2 Algorithmic

Given the ubiquity of randomness in science, a more flexible solution to randomness beyond hardware generation is desirable, not least for our ability as scientists to predictably test programmes we write (the very subject of this paper). Around the same time as RAND was producing its book of random digits, John von Neumann was working on the first Pseudorandom Number Generator (PRNG), predicting: “When random numbers are to be used in fast machines, number will usually be needed faster.” Von Neumann’s *middle square* method [VN51] is only of historical interest now, but is still used as inspiration for new PRNGs [Wid17].

Since von Neumann’s efforts, the search has continued for fast, memory-efficient and more random PRNGs. The Mersenne Twister (MT) [MN98] is commonly deployed in many programming languages and libraries (including Python and R), while Numpy now uses the Permuted Congruential Generator (PCG) [O’N14] as its default PRNG. There are a host of other PRNGs available [Lom08, BD22].

2.3 Statistical Testing

A large catalogue of statistical tests exist to vet the randomness of RNGs (both hardware and algorithmic). Knuth was the first to devise a series of tests for RNGs [Knu97], and at present there are three libraries/batteries of tests that are in common use: NIST STS [RSN⁺01], Dieharder [BEB14] (an update on the original Diehard [Mar95], now containing 110 tests) and TestU01 [LS07] (which includes the state-of-the-art *Big Crush* collection of 106 tests). RNGs are not expected to be able to pass all tests [LO19], and even the tests themselves are subject to rigorous testing [SOMK22].

Of course, the tests tell nothing of the true randomness of the stream provided for testing. Common mathematical constants such as π , e and $\sqrt{2}$ are able to pass these tests despite obviously not being random [Mar05], as are most rationals $\frac{k}{p}$ for large primes p .

²A valued contribution given how non-random humans tend to be [KP76].

³<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1cUUfMeOijg>

⁴See <https://www.2uo.de/myths-about-urandom/> and <https://sockpuppet.org/blog/2014/02/25/safely-generate-random-numbers/>.

⁵<https://git.kernel.org/pub/scm/linux/kernel/git/stable/linux.git/tree/drivers/char/random.c?id=refs/tags/v3.15.6#n52>

2.4 Cryptographically Secure Pseudorandom Number Generators

A PRNG's ability to pass statistical tests for randomness (such as BigCrush) may not make it suitable for certain tasks, however. While non-critical tasks, such as Monte Carlo simulation, may only require fast random number generation that passes Big Crush to be suitable, applications in cryptography and privacy may require further guarantees. RNGs need to pass two additional tests to be a Cryptographically Secure Pseudorandom Number Generator (CSPRNG) (or Cryptographic Pseudorandom Number Generator (CPRNG)): (i) that the next bit cannot be predicted from knowing the previous bits (the *next-bit test*, or *polynomial-time perfection* [L'E12]), and (ii) that the state of the RNG cannot be reverse-engineered from its outputs.

Commonly-used PRNGs are susceptible to state recovery by observing a sufficiently large sequence of output bits. Examples include the MT (whose state can be determined by observing 624 consecutive outputs [AK12]) and PCG (for which attacks taking 20 000 CPU hours have compromised its state [BMS20]). Hardware RNGs are typically robust from these state recovery attacks, since they lack any internal state and instead rely on the state of the universe for its randomness.⁶

CSPRNGs need not be used for every application however, since the added security they provide usually comes at the expense of computation time. Examples from the Rust programming language show CSPRNGs to be up to 200 times slower per byte of data than non-cryptographic variants,⁷ although other examples show a difference of just 50%.⁸

A common example of a CSPRNG is the AES block cipher in counter mode, which has been in use for two decades [HW03]. More recently, this idea of using counter-mode encryption protocols as RNGs has heralded a new class of generator, the Counter-Based Pseudorandom Number Generator (CBPRNG) [SMDS11]. The simple state space of these RNGs (just a counter and a key) is combined with simplifications in the cryptographic guarantees (e.g., 5-7 transformation rounds in ADS instead of the 10-14 rounds in AES) to construct a fast (albeit non-crypto-secure) PRNG suitable for simple parallelisation.

Other popular CSPRNGs include ChaCha [Ber08] and HC-128.

2.5 Relevance to Differential Privacy

When publishing DP outputs, it is preferable to use a CSPRNG to ensure maximum security against reverse engineering of the noise. For the purpose of testing, scientific publication and other controlled analysis where privacy of the underlying data is not of concern, it is sufficient to use a well-tested PRNG given the advantages in availability, execution time and reproducibility. The statistical quality of their randomness is taken care of by the statistical tests, as distinct from the cryptographic tests CSPRNGs must pass.

3 RANDOM NUMBER GENERATION AND SEEDING IN PYTHON AND NUMPY

We now give an overview of the specifics of RNGs, and their seeding, in Python and Numpy, given that they are the language and primary library used for building diffprivlib. While the specific implementation of RNGs will differ with other languages and libraries, we hope this outline will give sufficient principles-based insights to be adaptable to the reader's preferred tools.

⁶For the benefit of mankind, we assume the state of the universe to be unknowable.

⁷<https://docs.rs/nanorand/latest/nanorand/>

⁸<https://rust-random.github.io/book/guide-rngs.html>

3.1 random module

The default package for random number generation in Python is the Random module.⁹ Random uses the MT PRNG as its core generator (with a period of $2^{19937} - 1$), and is invoked by instantiating a generator (`random.Random()`) with which sampling procedures can be executed (e.g., `random()`, `randint()` and `normalvariate()`). Alternatively, the sampling procedures can be called directly from module methods (e.g., `random.randint()`).¹⁰

The generator can be seeded with the `seed` method (i.e., `random.Random().seed()`), which sets the state of the MT. If no seed is provided (or a `None` seed), the generator is seeded with operating system randomness (i.e., `/dev/random`), or, otherwise, the current time and process ID.¹¹ This ensures pseudorandomness without user-driven seeding, in contrast to other languages such as C which are not seeded by default (meaning repeated execution of scripts with `rand` will give the same outputs).

3.2 secrets module

Arising from the weak security guarantees of the MT RNG and the apparent misuse of the module in security-critical tasks, the Secrets module was added to Python in 2015 as a user-friendly CSPRNG using `/dev/random` (in Unix) or `CryptGenRandom()` (in Windows).¹² As this module uses OS-generated randomness, it is neither necessary nor possible to seed the generator. However, on most machines, it is the most secure way to generate random bits and should be preferred for security-critical tasks. However, for tasks require reproducible results, Secrets is not suitable.

3.3 Numpy

Numpy is a popular library for scientific computing in Python, supporting calculations on large multidimensional arrays and an extensive library of mathematical functions [vdWCV11]. Prior to Numpy v1.17, `RandomState` was the class for generating randomness, containing both bit generation (using the MT, like Python) and bit transformation functionality. Each of the bit transformers (e.g., `random_integers()` and `standard_normal()`) can also be called directly from the `numpy.random` module.¹³

Since Numpy v1.17,¹⁴ the bit generation and bit transformation functionality has been divided between the `BitGenerator` and `Generator` classes respectively. This allows for the implementation of different RNGs that subclass the `BitGenerator` class, while leveraging the common distribution sampling functionality of `Generator` . As of Numpy v1.25, five bit generators are natively supported, including MT and PCG. A third-party package, `randomgen`, having started as a project to modernise Numpy's Random module, has a number of additional Numpy-compatible PRNGs and CSPRNGs.¹⁵

⁹<https://docs.python.org/3/library/random.html>

¹⁰In this case, the generator instance is stored in the `random._inst` variable, so `random.random()` is equivalent to `random._inst.random()`, etc.

¹¹https://github.com/python/cpython/blob/3.11/Modules/_randommodule.c#L284-L290

¹²<https://peps.python.org/pep-0506/>

¹³These are called from the pre-initialised instance of `RandomState` at `numpy.random._rand` .

¹⁴See [release notes for v1.17](#), corresponding [NEP 19](#) and pull request [GH13163](#).

¹⁵<https://github.com/bashtage/randomgen>

When a bit generator is seeded by the user, that seed is used to initialise a new `SeedSequence` object.¹⁶ A seed sequence mixes the entropy of the provided seed(s) (through iterative hashing and mixing),¹⁷ allowing the `BitGenerator` to request the entropy required to seed itself (e.g., 624 32-bit integers for MT, or two 64-bit integers for PCG). There is no limit to the size of integer a seed sequence can be seeded with.¹⁸ If a seed is not explicitly provided, 128 random bits are drawn from `Secrets` to be used as the seed.¹⁹

3.4 Other Python libraries

Scipy, another popular Python library for scientific computing, uses Numpy for underlying randomness (with support for both `RandomState` and `Generator`) and adds extra functionality with its `stats` module [VGO⁺20].²⁰ TensorFlow, a library primarily used for the training and inference of deep neural networks, has a standalone RNG module, with support for two CBPRNGs [AAB⁺15, SMDS11].²¹

4 SEEDING PITFALLS

Given humans' inability to select digits uniformly at random, it should come as no surprise that we as a species has a special affinity with certain integers as seeds for RNGs. A number of studies²² have shown the distribution of seeds chosen "randomly" weighs heavily on 0, 1, 42²³ and 1234²⁴. C++ users appear especially attached to the seed 380 843, although this author, like others, was unable to get to the bottom of its origins.

4.1 Seeding for security and bias mitigation

Seeding our RNGs even with 32-bit integers (up to 4 294 967 296) presents an immediate security risk, even if a CSPRNG is being used, as it opens the possibility of the seed being determined by brute force.

Aside from security risks, seeding with fewer bits than the internal state risk bias in the random numbers generated. This may affect the randomness of the RNG and have an unanticipated effect in tests and experiments. For example, using an MT19937 RNG to sample 32-bit integers, it will never produce 7 nor 3 as the first output if it were seeded with a single 32-bit integer!²⁵ Since the internal state of an MT19937 is 624 32-bit integers, it should be no surprise that seeding with only 32 bits will leave holes in its output space. Other defects of seeded RNGs have been found through simulations of baseball games [MWKA07].

¹⁶https://github.com/numpy/numpy/blob/v1.25.0/numpy/random/bit_generator.pyx#L533

¹⁷Numpy's implementation (<https://github.com/numpy/numpy/pull/13780>) is derived from Melissa E. O'Neill's design (https://www.pcg-random.org/posts/developing-a-seed_seq-alternative.html).

¹⁸Within Numpy, `SeedSequence` handles a large integer seeds by splitting them into an array of 32-bit Numpy integers (lowest bits first – with `_int_to_uint32_array()`), which is then used to generate an RNG's state. System memory is therefore the only limiting factor in the initial seed size.

¹⁹See https://github.com/numpy/numpy/blob/v1.25.0/numpy/random/bit_generator.pyx#L302.

²⁰<https://docs.scipy.org/doc/scipy-1.11.1/reference/stats.html>

²¹https://www.tensorflow.org/versions/r2.12/api_docs/python/tf/random

²²<https://www.kaggle.com/code/residentmario/kernel16e284dc7>, <https://blog.semicolonsoftware.de/the-most-popular-random-seeds/> and <https://www.residentmar.io/2016/07/08/randomly-popular.html>

²³The Answer to the Ultimate Question of Life, the Universe, and Everything: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Phrases_from_The_Hitchhiker%27s_Guide_to_the_Galaxy.

²⁴The kind of combination an idiot would have on their luggage: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=a6iW-8xPw3k>.

²⁵<https://www.pcg-random.org/posts/cpp-seeding-surprises.html>

```

1 >>> from numpy.random import SeedSequence, PCG64, Generator
2 >>> SeedSequence().entropy
3 287955962967732827663192315245491885249
4 >>> rng = Generator(PCG64(287955962967732827663192315245491885249))
5 >>> rng.random()
6 0.07296271584154868

```

Listing 1. Using `SeedSequence` to seed an RNG in Numpy.

Numpy. The use of `SeedSequence` is advised in Numpy (see Section 3.3). It is recommended to initialise a `SeedSequence` object without a seed (for which the `Secrets` package is used to extract randomness) and a seed can then be extracted via the `entropy` attribute to generate a static seed for use in downstream tasks (see Listing 1).²⁶ This should reduce the chance of bias in results, and eliminate it in the case of RNGs that have a 128-bit internal state (*i.e.*, PCG).

4.2 Seeding for parallel processes

The generation of random numbers in parallel applications has been an area of active research for decades [DMP88, Hel98, SMDS11, LMOS17], and requires considerable caution to be observed. There are a number of techniques for producing parallel (sub-)streams, the most common of which are (i) single stream, (ii) multi-stream, and (iii) substream [LMOS17, SMDS11].

Using a single stream is not advised, due to speed and reproducibility limitations. Multistreaming can be achieved by parametrising a local stream for each computational unit. This can be done deterministically (*i.e.*, using a thread ID as a key for a CBPRNG), or by using a randomly generated seed. Random seeding is particularly useful when generators must be created on-the-fly (although care must be taken to avoid the “birthday problem” [McK66] of re-using the same stream). In most situations, the probability of overlapping streams is negligible [LMOS17].

Substreaming can be achieved in two ways. With *leap-frogging* (or *striding*), task $t \in [T]$ gets all integers n_i satisfying $i \bmod T = t$ (*i.e.*, every T th sample). Either each task is required to consume one value at each step, or each task can advance its own generator by T steps each time, a typically time consuming process. Alternatively, with *blocking*, task t gets N integers n_i where $i \in [tN, (t+1)N - 1]$. This requires the RNG to have a jump-ahead function, which is not universal. Care must also be taken that the same blocks are not re-used, particularly when iteratively or adaptively blocking (*i.e.*, a grandchild sharing the same block as their aunt).

Numpy. The `SeedSequence` object is again recommended to generate seeds for parallel generation in Numpy,²⁷ taking advantage of the uniqueness of outputs to avoid the birthday problem. It is also an explicit, user-friendly way to seed the parallel generators, and should be easy to follow from a cursory reading of the code. With `SeedSequence`, new seeds can be generated from the child RNG, allowing for grandchild and great-grandchild processes to be spawned without having to pre-allocate space and without running the risk of overlapping streams.²⁸

²⁶https://numpy.org/doc/1.25/reference/random/bit_generators/generated/numpy.random.SeedSequence.html

²⁷<https://numpy.org/doc/1.25/reference/random/parallel.html>

²⁸Each seed sequence is given a unique key that tracks its position in the tree of sequences spawned from the root (*i.e.*, the first grandchild from a first child sequence is given the key $(0, 0)$) while using the same entropy. The `spawn_key` is mixed with the entropy pool to create a unique pool of randomness for each spawned RNG: https://github.com/numpy/numpy/blob/v1.25.0/numpy/random/bit_generator.pyx#L308-L313.

Since Numpy v1.25, a `Generator` class instance can be used to spawn child generators for parallel computation using the `spawn()` method,²⁹ while older versions of Numpy can use the `BitGenerator`'s `_seed_seq` attribute to access the RNG's underlying seed sequence (which can be used to spawn new sequences with which to initialise new generators).³⁰

Numpy also supports blocking of some RNGs using the `jumped()` method (spawning a new RNG whose state has been jumped as if 2^{128} – or $(\phi - 1)2^{128}$ for PCG – random numbers have been drawn).

5 SEEDING IN DIFFPRIVLIB

We have two priorities in implementing seeded random number generation in `diffprivlib`. Firstly, to maintain a consistent, user-friendly interface for seeding across all `diffprivlib` functions, and equally importantly, the ability to use a cryptographically secure source of randomness for DP noise generation (e.g., using `Secrets`) in sensitive tasks. Thankfully, precedent exists in both Numpy (Section 3.3) and Scikit-Learn for seeding, and leveraging this has simplified the engineering challenge for `diffprivlib`.

Support for RNG seeding was added in `diffprivlib` v0.6.³¹

5.1 Lessons from Scikit-Learn and Numpy

The core philosophy behind RNG seeding in Numpy and Scikit-Learn is the ability to pass an single RNG instance to a function/method, and have it persist and propagate through all calls and sub-calls within its logic. This RNG instance is what governs all elements of randomness within that function/method, whether specifically relied upon for DP or not. This ensures the user has full control over the randomness of a particular function, and the randomness of different function calls within the same script, if required.³² This provides more flexibility and control, and (importantly for this paper) gives an explicit method for seeding that should be clear from a cursory reading of the code. It also allows for multiple streams to be maintained without cross-contamination. This is also consistent with established software engineering practices of prioritising local variables over globals [MC09], as they can reduce flexibility and modularity of code.

In terms of implementation, each `diffprivlib` function takes a `random_state` parameter which can be (i) `None`, (ii) a non-negative integer, or (iii) a `RandomState` instance. The `random_state` parameter is ingested by the `check_random_state()` function. When a `RandomState` instance is provided, that instance is used as the generator, updating its state when deployed.

If the provided random state is an integer, `check_random_state()` creates a new `RandomState` instance, seeded with that integer. If no seed is provided (or `seed=None`), the `numpy.random.mtrand._rand` instance is returned. The returned instance is then used for all calls within the function, and any calls derived from it.

There is an important distinction between providing integer-valued seeds and `RandomState` instances that are worth highlighting.³³ Integer-valued seeds are a great way to produce the same outputs for repeat calls of the same function. Consider the code using a (poorly-chosen, per Section 4) integer-valued seed in Listing 2 and the corresponding output when parametrising

²⁹<https://github.com/numpy/numpy/pull/23195>

³⁰<https://github.com/numpy/numpy/issues/15322#issuecomment-626400433>

³¹<https://github.com/IBM/differential-privacy-library/releases/tag/0.6.0>

³²As described in more detail by Numpy developer Robert Kern (see thread of comments): <https://stackoverflow.com/a/5837352>.

³³Further details are available here: https://scikit-learn.org/1.2/common_pitfalls.html#controlling-randomness.

```

1 >>> from diffprivlib.mechanisms import Laplace
2 >>> Laplace(epsilon=1, sensitivity=1, random_state=1).randomise(1)
3 0.6556851745442447
4 >>> Laplace(epsilon=1, sensitivity=1, random_state=1).randomise(1)
5 0.6556851745442447

```

Listing 2. Seeding a diffprivlib mechanism with an integer giving the same output.

```

1 >>> from diffprivlib.utils import check_random_state
2 >>> rng = check_random_state(1)
3 >>> Laplace(epsilon=1, sensitivity=1, random_state=rng).randomise(1)
4 0.6556851745442447
5 >>> Laplace(epsilon=1, sensitivity=1, random_state=rng).randomise(1)
6 1.2482045505881658

```

Listing 3. Using an RNG instance with a diffprivlib mechanism gives unique (but reproducible) outputs.

with a persistent `RandomState` instance in Listing 3. In the latter, the function calls are no longer returning the same output, but running the same *script* again will consistently produce the same output. In most cases, this behaviour is what is desired.

5.2 Limitations with Scikit-Learn

There are a number of issues presented by Scikit-Learn’s approach to random number generation that limits our adoption of best practices in diffprivlib.

Legacy random state. Firstly, only the legacy `RandomState` interface is natively supported by Scikit-Learn.³⁴ This limits the generator to the slower MT19937, and excludes the better RNGs introduced in Numpy v1.17 (or any other custom RNGs). It is possible to work around this RNG limitation by explicitly specifying a `BitGenerator` as a seed for a `RandomState` instance (*i.e.*, `np.random.RandomState(np.random.PCG64(seed))`), assuming the required version of Numpy is installed.³⁵ However, at present, there is no method to deploy a `Generator` instance, and make use of its superior bit transformations.³⁶

Low-bit seeds. Another downside to Scikit-Learn’s present approach to seeding is its limitation to 32-bit seeds.³⁷ This limitation appears to be arbitrary, since the seed is directly passed to a `RandomState` instance which routinely accepts larger integer seeds (that are passed straight through to a `SeedSequence` instance to generate the required randomness bit-count). Additionally, it is at odds with Numpy’s preferred practice of using the entropy of a `SeedSequence`, itself a 128-bit integer. A workaround to this is again to pass the seed (or seed sequence) directly to

³⁴The Scikit-Learn community is considering supporting Numpy’s `BitGenerator` for randomness ([GH16988](https://github.com/scikit-learn/scikit-learn/pull/16988) and [GH20669](https://github.com/scikit-learn/scikit-learn/pull/20669)) as is Scipy ([GH14322](https://github.com/scipy/scipy/pull/14322)).

³⁵As of Scikit-Learn v1.1, Numpy v1.17 is a minimum requirement.

³⁶Nevertheless, issues for DP may persist, including floating-point vulnerabilities [[HB21](https://github.com/scikit-learn/scikit-learn/pull/21)].

³⁷Not only are seeds larger than 32 bits unsupported (<https://github.com/scikit-learn/scikit-learn/pull/1548>), but supplying one is met with an uninformative `TypeError` (a fix for which is in progress at time of writing, [GH26648](https://github.com/scikit-learn/scikit-learn/pull/26648)).

the `BitGenerator`, which can then be passed to the `RandomState`. It is planned to add this workaround to `diffprivlib` in due course.

5.3 Deploying Secrets

As outlined in Section 3.2, the `Secrets` module is the best source of cryptographically-secure randomness in Python, thanks to its hardware-generated pools of randomness entropy. From a privacy perspective, the only application of randomness that needs to be secured is that relating to DP, although care must be given to other aspects of randomness which may be relied upon for DP (e.g., privacy amplification through shuffling [EFM⁺19]). In `diffprivlib`, most of the important DP noise additions happen within the `mechanisms` module.

For reproducibility purposes, we must use the relevant `RandomState` instance whenever a seed has been supplied, but use `Secrets` with `diffprivlib`-specific components if a seed hasn't been supplied. This can be done with relative ease because the default `RandomState` returned when `seed=None` is the one stored at `numpy.random.mtrand._rand`;³⁸ if this is the same as the supplied RNG to the mechanism, we know to override the RNG with `Secrets`.

One final consideration when allowing for secrets to be used on-the-fly are the differences in sampling function names. The interface of `SystemRandom` (as used by `Secrets`) differs from that used by `RandomState`, requiring the use of `try...except` statements wherever a difference occurs (thankfully, both interfaces employ `random()` for uniform variate sampling).

6 CONCLUSION AND TL;DR

Differential Privacy (DP) practitioners are encouraged to support the seeding of Random Number Generators (RNGs) to allow for reproduction of any published work (using open, non-sensitive data), and to help with testing and debugging. Choosing any rigorously-tested Pseudorandom Number Generator (PRNG) is likely to be sufficient, but special care must be taken when seeding (especially for parallel computations).

Be sure to seed the RNG with many random bits to avoid biased outcomes. When seeding RNGs for parallel computations, use a seed sequence if possible (they have many benefits, including that they are bijective, and can spawn non-overlapping streams with ease). Otherwise, block the RNG (using a jump-ahead function like `jumped()`) while keeping track of previously-assigned blocks to avoid overlaps.

Lastly, to enable safe DP releases “in the wild”, allow for the use of a Cryptographically Secure Pseudorandom Number Generator (CSPRNG) for the secure generation of noise whenever a seed is not provided.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant number 951911 – AI4Media.

REFERENCES

- [AAB⁺15] ABADI, M., AGARWAL, A., BARHAM, P., BREVDO, E., CHEN, Z., CITRO, C., CORRADO, G. S., DAVIS, A., DEAN, J., DEVIN, M., GHEMAWAT, S., GOODFELLOW, I., HARP, A., IRVING, G., ISARD, M., JOZEFOWICZ, R., JIA, Y., KAISER, L., KUDLUR, M., LEVENBERG, J., MANÉ, D., SCHUSTER, M., MONGA, R., MOORE, S., MURRAY, D., OLAH, C., SHLENS, J., STEINER, B., SUTSKEVER, I., TALWAR, K., TUCKER, P., VANHOUCHE, V., VASUDEVAN, V., VIÉGAS, F., VINYALS, O.,

³⁸The stability of this feature for Scikit-Learn now seems to be considered a mistake: <https://numpy.org/neps/nep-0019-rng-policy.html#numpy-random>.

- WARDEN, P., WATTENBERG, M., WICKE, M., YU, Y., AND ZHENG, X. TensorFlow, large-scale machine learning on heterogeneous systems, Nov. 2015.
- [ABE08] ARUZ, J., BENZEL, K., AND EVANS, J. M. *Beyond Babylon: art, trade, and diplomacy in the second millennium BC*. Metropolitan Museum of Art, 2008.
- [AK12] ARGYROS, G., AND KIAYIAS, A. I forgot your password: Randomness attacks against PHP applications. In *USENIX Security Symposium* (2012), pp. 81–96.
- [BD22] BHATTACHARJEE, K., AND DAS, S. A search for good pseudo-random number generators: Survey and empirical studies. *Computer Science Review* 45 (2022), 100471.
- [BEB14] BROWN, R. G., EDELBUETTEL, D., AND BAUER, D. Dieharder: A random number test suite (version 3.31.1). <http://www.phy.duke.edu/~rgb/General/dieharder.php> (2014), 1.
- [Ber08] BERNSTEIN, D. J. ChaCha, a variant of Salsa20. In *Workshop record of SASC* (2008), vol. 8, Citeseer, pp. 3–5.
- [BMS20] BOUILLAGUET, C., MARTINEZ, F., AND SAUVAGE, J. Practical seed-recovery for the PCG pseudo-random number generator. *IACR Transactions on Symmetric Cryptology* (2020).
- [Dev86] DEVROYE, L. *Non-uniform random variate generation*. Springer-Verlag, New York, 1986.
- [DMP88] DE MATTEIS, A., AND PAGNUTTI, S. Parallelization of random number generators and long-range correlations. *Numerische Mathematik* 53 (1988), 595–608.
- [EFM⁺19] ERLINGSSON, Ú., FELDMAN, V., MIRONOV, I., RAGHUNATHAN, A., TALWAR, K., AND THAKURTA, A. *Amplification by Shuffling: From Local to Central Differential Privacy via Anonymity*. SIAM, 2019, pp. 2468–2479.
- [Gen03] GENTLE, J. E. *Random number generation and Monte Carlo methods*, vol. 381. Springer, 2003.
- [GL20] GARFINKEL, S. L., AND LECLERC, P. Randomness concerns when deploying differential privacy. In *Proceedings of the 19th Workshop on Privacy in the Electronic Society* (New York, NY, USA, 2020), WPES’20, Association for Computing Machinery, p. 73–86.
- [HB21] HOLOHAN, N., AND BRAGHIN, S. Secure random sampling in differential privacy. In *Computer Security - ESORICS 2021 - 26th European Symposium on Research in Computer Security, Darmstadt, Germany, October 4-8, 2021, Proceedings, Part II* (2021), E. Bertino, H. Shulman, and M. Waidner, Eds., vol. 12973 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, Springer, pp. 523–542.
- [HBMAL19] HOLOHAN, N., BRAGHIN, S., MAC AONGHUSA, P., AND LEVACHER, K. Diffprivlib: the IBM differential privacy library. *ArXiv e-prints 1907.02444 [cs.CR]* (July 2019).
- [HDH⁺22] HANEY, S., DESFONTAINES, D., HARTMAN, L., SHRESTHA, R., AND HAY, M. Precision-based attacks and interval refining: how to break, then fix, differential privacy on finite computers. *ArXiv e-prints 2207.13793 [cs.CR]* (2022).
- [Hel98] HELLEKALEK, P. Don’t trust parallel Monte Carlo! In *Proceedings of the Twelfth Workshop on Parallel and Distributed Simulation* (USA, 1998), PADS ’98, IEEE Computer Society, p. 82–89.
- [HLD04] HÖRMANN, W., LEYDOLD, J., AND DERFLINGER, G. *Automatic nonuniform random variate generation*. Statistics and Computing. Springer, 2004.
- [HW03] HELLEKALEK, P., AND WEGENKITTL, S. Empirical evidence concerning AES. *ACM Trans. Model. Comput. Simul.* 13, 4 (oct 2003), 322–333.
- [JMRO22] JIN, J., MCMURTRY, E., RUBINSTEIN, B. I. P., AND OHRIMENKO, O. Are we there yet? Timing and floating-point attacks on differential privacy systems. In *2022 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)* (2022), pp. 473–488.
- [KMR⁺20] KIFER, D., MESSING, S., ROTH, A., THAKURTA, A., AND ZHANG, D. Guidelines for implementing and auditing differentially private systems. *ArXiv e-prints 2002.04049 [cs.CR]* (Feb. 2020).
- [Knu97] KNUTH, D. E. *The Art of Computer Programming, Volume 2 (3rd Ed.): Seminumerical Algorithms*. Addison-Wesley Longman Publishing Co., Inc., USA, 1997.
- [KP76] KUBOVY, M., AND PSOTKA, J. The predominance of seven and the apparent spontaneity of numerical choices. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance* 2, 2 (1976), 291.
- [KŠM07] KRHOVJÁK, J., ŠVENDA, P., AND MATYÁŠ, V. The sources of randomness in mobile devices. In *Proceedings of the 12th Nordic Workshop on Secure IT Systems. NordSec* (2007).
- [L’E94] L’ECUYER, P. Uniform random number generation. *Annals of Operations Research* 53 (1994), 77–120.
- [L’E98] L’ECUYER, P. Random number generation. In *Handbook of simulation: principles, methodology, advances, applications, and practice*, J. Banks, Ed. Wiley, 1998, pp. 93–137.
- [L’E12] L’ECUYER, P. *Random number generation*. Springer, 2012.
- [LMOS17] L’ECUYER, P., MUNGER, D., ORESHKIN, B., AND SIMARD, R. Random numbers for parallel computers: Requirements and methods, with emphasis on GPUs. *Mathematics and Computers in Simulation* 135 (2017), 3–17. Special Issue: 9th IMACS Seminar on Monte Carlo Methods.
- [LO19] LEMIRE, D., AND O’NEILL, M. E. Xorshift1024*, xorshift1024+, xorshift128+ and xoroshiro128+ fail statistical tests for linearity. *J. Comput. Appl. Math.* 350 (2019), 139–142.

- [Lom08] LOMONT, C. Random number generation. https://lomont.org/papers/2008/Lomont_PRNG_2008.pdf (2008).
- [LS07] L'ECUYER, P., AND SIMARD, R. TestU01: A C library for empirical testing of random number generators. *ACM Trans. Math. Softw.* 33, 4 (aug 2007).
- [Mar95] MARSAGLIA, G. Diehard battery of tests of randomness. <https://web.archive.org/web/20120102192622/www.stat.fsu.edu/pub/diehard> (1995).
- [Mar05] MARSAGLIA, G. On the randomness of π and other decimal expansions. *InterStat* 5 (2005).
- [MC09] MARTIN, R. C., AND COPLIEN, J. O. *Clean code: a handbook of agile software craftsmanship*. Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, NJ [etc.], 2009.
- [McK66] MCKINNEY, E. H. Generalized birthday problem. *The American Mathematical Monthly* 73, 4 (1966), 385–387.
- [MN98] MATSUMOTO, M., AND NISHIMURA, T. Mersenne twister: A 623-dimensionally equidistributed uniform pseudo-random number generator. *ACM Trans. Model. Comput. Simul.* 8, 1 (1998), 3–30.
- [MWKA07] MATSUMOTO, M., WADA, I., KURAMOTO, A., AND ASHIHARA, H. Common defects in initialization of pseudorandom number generators. *ACM Transactions on Modeling and Computer Simulation (TOMACS)* 17, 4 (2007), 15–es.
- [MYC⁺16] MA, X., YUAN, X., CAO, Z., QI, B., AND ZHANG, Z. Quantum random number generation. *npj Quantum Information* 2, 1 (2016), 1–9.
- [NCP03] NOLL, L. C., COOPER, S., AND PLEASANT, M. What is LavaRnd. <http://www.lavarnd.org> (2003).
- [Nie92] NIEDERREITER, H. *Random Number Generation and Quasi-Monte Carlo Methods*. Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics, 1992.
- [NMS98] NOLL, L. C., MENDE, R. G., AND SISODIYA, S. Method for seeding a pseudo-random number generator with a cryptographic hash of a digitization of a chaotic system, Mar. 24 1998. US Patent 5,732,138.
- [O'N14] O'NEILL, M. E. PCG: A family of simple fast space-efficient statistically good algorithms for random number generation. Tech. Rep. HMC-CS-2014-0905, Harvey Mudd College, Claremont, CA, Sept. 2014.
- [RAN55] RAND CORPORATION. *A million random digits with 100,000 normal deviates*. Free Press, 1955.
- [RSN⁺01] RUKHIN, A., SOTO, J., NECHVATAL, J., SMID, M., AND BARKER, E. A statistical test suite for random and pseudorandom number generators for cryptographic applications. Tech. rep., Booz-allen and hamilton inc mclean va, 2001.
- [SMDS11] SALMON, J. K., MORAES, M. A., DROR, R. O., AND SHAW, D. E. Parallel random numbers: as easy as 1, 2, 3. In *Proceedings of 2011 international conference for high performance computing, networking, storage and analysis* (2011), pp. 1–12.
- [SOMK22] ŠÝS, M., OBRÁTIL, L., MATYÁŠ, V., AND KLINEC, D. A bad day to die hard: Correcting the dieharder battery. *Journal of Cryptology* 35 (2022), 1–20.
- [Tez95] TEZUKA, S. *Uniform Random Numbers: Theory and Practice*. Springer Science+Business Media, New York, 1995.
- [vdWCV11] VAN DER WALT, S., COLBERT, S. C., AND VAROQUAUX, G. The NumPy array: A structure for efficient numerical computation. *Computing in Science and Engineering* 13, 2 (2011), 22–30.
- [VGO⁺20] VIRTANEN, P., GOMMERS, R., OLIPHANT, T. E., HABERLAND, M., REDDY, T., COURNAPEAU, D., BUROVSKI, E., PETERSON, P., WECKESSER, W., BRIGHT, J., VAN DER WALT, S. J., BRETT, M., WILSON, J., MILLMAN, K. J., MAYOROV, N., NELSON, A. R. J., JONES, E., KERN, R., LARSON, E., CAREY, C. J., POLAT, İ., FENG, Y., MOORE, E. W., VANDERPLAS, J., LAXALDE, D., PERKTOLD, J., CIMRMAN, R., HENRIKSEN, I., QUINTERO, E. A., HARRIS, C. R., ARCHIBALD, A. M., RIBEIRO, A. H., PEDREGOSA, F., VAN MULBREGT, P., AND SCI-PY 1.0 CONTRIBUTORS. SciPy 1.0: Fundamental algorithms for scientific computing in Python. *Nature Methods* 17 (2020), 261–272.
- [VN51] VON NEUMANN, J. Various techniques used in connection with random digits. *Applied Math Series* 12, 36-38 (1951), 1.
- [Wid17] WIDYNSKI, B. Middle-square Weyl sequence RNG. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1704.00358* (2017).